

Report on services offered on IO, coupling and workflow

Deliverable D3.3

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1 Abstract/publishable summary

Task 3.3 from work package 3 “Service 2: Coupling, IO and workflows” offered to the weather and climate modelling community dedicated support to optimally use the following community tools: the OASIS3-MCT coupler, the XIOS IO server, and the Cylc workflow engine.

Regarding OASIS3-MCT, support was granted to the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC, Norway) to implement a coupling between an ocean global configuration and two hemispheric sea ice models, setting the basis of a future NEMO-neXtSIM ocean/sea-ice coupled model. Support was also offered to the UK Meteorological Office (Met Office) to start the development of a 3D coupling between NEMO and the MEDUSA biogeochemistry module.

Regarding XIOS, the support provided to the UK Met Office resulted in improved support for unstructured grid in XIOS, directly benefiting the next-generation atmospheric model LFRIC. Also, improvement of XIOS input functionality was realised in support of Mercator Océan (France), motivated by the need to efficiently read in higher-frequency higher-resolution ERA5 reanalysis fields.

Finally, Cylc developers helped two groups one at the Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) in Poland and one at the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) in UK, to use more efficiently the Cylc workflow engine in their respective Earth System Model and, for NCAS, to port it on a new architecture (ARCHER2).

2 Conclusion & Results

All supports lead to very positive results, from the point of view of both the coupled models and the tools themselves.

Regarding NERSC support on OASIS3-MCT, the implementation of a 3-model coupled system is completed involving the NEMO ocean model and two SI3 hemispheric ice models. The set-up is therefore ready to be adapted to the neXtSIM model, as soon as it will migrate from its current Lagrangian grid to an Arakawa grid, in the framework of the on-going SASIP project.

The support to the UK Met Office targeted 3D coupling between the NEMO ocean model and a lower-resolution (coarsened) biogeochemistry (BGC) module. For the last NEMO version (4.2), the support has permitted the phasing of code allowing this type of coupling, the easy generation of the coarsened input files, and the creation of the weight-and-address files used for the 3D regridding between the original grid and the coarsened grid. These developments were validated with one-month simulation performed with NEMO coupled to PISCES BGC module that can now, as the next step, be replaced by the UK Met Office MEDUSA BGC module.

The service on XIOS to the UK Met Office resulted in the full support of unstructured grid by XIOS, essential for LFRIC and now available in the last version of the IO server, XIOS3.

The improvement of XIOS for reading input files, realized thanks to the service offered to Mercator Océan, allows a significant acceleration of the reads, by a factor of almost 3 in some configurations. Furthermore, the switch from XIOS2 to XIOS3 also showed significant gains in the simulation time and a major reduction (of up to a factor of 3) in the memory footprint on XIOS servers.

The Cylc services, originally planned with 3 person month (PMs) to ICM and 3 PMs to NCAS, were finally delivered for only 1 PM to each group in the timeframe of the project. The support offered to ICM has allowed an easy use of Cylc in their workflow. Cylc developers remain in contact with ICM to facilitate the migration to Cylc-8. The support to NCAS for installing and configuring Cylc and providing Cylc-8 training has been delayed due to waiting time for getting the new PUMA server setup on ARCHER2 by its support team. The bulk of the Cylc installation work was delayed until January 2023 and will be continued until the end of ESiWACE2.

Overall, the services enhanced the HPC capacity of the weather and climate community and also, thanks to

the support on XIOS and Cylc, helped it to manage data produced by its simulations.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in Section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	X
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This document presents an overview of the services provided on community tools supported in ESiWACE2: the OASIS3-MCT coupler (Valcke et al., 2021a), the XIOS IO server¹, and the Cylc workflow engine². This deliverable is associated to work package 3 (WP3) Task 3.3 "Service 2: Coupling, IO and workflows". Overall, 4, 2 and 2 PMs of dedicated support were provided respectively on the coupler, the IO server and the workflow engine directly by the tool developers.

4.1 OASIS3-MCT

In the first call in 2020, 2 PMs of dedicated support were granted to NERSC (Norway) to set the basis of a NEMO-neXtSIM ocean/sea-ice coupled model, for the implementation of a coupling between an ocean global configuration and two hemispheric sea ice models. In the second call, in 2022, 2 PMs were devoted to start developing a 3D coupling between the NEMO ocean model and the MEDUSA biogeochemistry model for the UK Met Office. These two services were offered remotely as the Covid pandemic did not allow easy on-site visits.

¹<http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver>

²<https://cylc.github.io>

4.1.1 Coupling NEMO global ocean with hemispheric Arctic and Antarctic sea-ice models

The details of this service are described in the full report by Maisonnave and Bourdallé-Badie (2022).

The objective here is ultimately to couple the NEMO ocean model and the neXtSIM sea ice model (Rampal et al., 2016), which spatial discretization is currently being transformed from a Lagrangian grid to an Eulerian one. One important decision, which had a strong impact on the technical set-up, was to use the same numerical grid for the ocean and the sea-ice models. This was motivated by the necessity to exactly conserve fluxes and surface variables at the ocean/sea-ice interface, in order to represent accurately near shore phenomena such as leads and polynyas, which is one of neXtSIM main scientific objective. Even if the coupler can perform accurate and locally conservative regridding, any land-sea mask mismatch between the ocean and the sea-ice model would necessarily lead to incoherencies and errors in these near-shore areas. Imposing the same grids in the two models is the most direct way to get rid of these potential incoherencies.

However, the NEMO ocean grid, called ORCA, is a tripolar grid with a particular North pole folding involving specific numerics that would be complex to implement in neXtSIM. To address this issue, it was decided to discretise the neXtSIM model on two hemispheric grids corresponding to the ORCA grid split at the equator. A new ordering of the ORCA Northern Hemisphere (ONH) grid points removes the North pole folding and allows to treat the domain as a closed regional grid, since no sea ice should be found at its equatorial boundary. The ORCA Southern Hemisphere (OSH) grid corresponds to a longitude-latitude grid and therefore only a simple cyclic boundary condition update needs to be implemented at its eastern and western boundaries. Figure 1 illustrates the transformation of the ORCA grid in the two ONH and OSH hemispheric grids, implemented in a dedicated transformation tool (i.e. not part of the coupler itself).

Figure 1: Transformation of the ORCA grid into two hemispheric grids, the ORCA Northern Hemisphere (ONH) and the ORCA Southern Hemisphere (OSH) grids. On the left, the ORCA global grid is represented with its North Pole Folding area. On the right, the two hemispheric grids formed of the same grid points but ordered differently are shown. At the center, the intermediate step transforming the upper part of the ORCA global grid into the ONH grid, removing its North Pole Folding is illustrated.

In addition to ensuring the perfect conservation of the coupled quantities exchanged (thanks to the exact correspondance between the points of the ocean and sea-ice grids), this set-up favours computing performance, as it avoids any regridding computation. It also simplifies the neXtSIM MPI parallelisation coding, as it remains ocean-model-agnostic and does not have to support the North pole folding.

To test this 3-component coupled model, it was first implemented between NEMO and SI3, the sea-ice

model usually imbedded in NEMO that can also be run as a stand-alone surface (SAS) module. The report (Maisonnavé and Bourdallé-Badie, 2022) describes in detail that work, realised as ESiWACE2 support, that lead to a coupled model assembling one global NEMO ocean model running on an ORCA2 grid (182x149 horizontal grid points) and two SAS modules, each one running on one hemispheric grid. That report presents the details of the coupling set-up, the tool developed to define the numbering of the hemispheric grids based on the global grid and the performance of the new set-up (CPL) compared to the single-executable model (SE) where the SI3 sea-ice is embedded in the NEMO ocean model. These measurements show that the CPL configuration gives comparable or better results than the SE one with up to 30% of speedup in some cases. The improvement comes from the extra level of macro-task parallelism in the CPL case, with two hemispheric sea-ice models running concurrently with the ocean, where as in the SE case, one global sea-ice model runs sequentially with respect to the ocean model into which it is embedded.

In conclusion, this support has led to a coupled configuration that, thanks to OASIS3-MCT flexibility, will be easily adapted to include the neXtSIM sea-ice model, instead of SI3, as soon as this model will be discretised on the Arakawa grids. We note that the NEMO ocean model coupling interface is also ready to technically receive fluxes from an atmosphere model, opening the door to a complete ocean/sea-ice/atmosphere climate model, which is one aim of the SASIP project³.

4.1.2 Biogeochemistry coarsening in NEMO 4.2

The details of this service are described in Maisonnavé and Berthet (2022). This support aimed to help the UK Met Office to adopt, in their 3D coupling between the NEMO ocean model and the MEDUSA biogeochemistry (BGC) model (Yool et al., 2013), the same coarser resolution for MEDUSA than the one used between NEMO and PISCES BGC models. Preliminary work had allowed to split PISCES and run it into a separated executable coupled via the OASIS library (Maisonnavé, 2020) and adapting coupling interfaces to a coarsening algorithm in such a way that it was possible to reduce the BGC resolution to 1/3 of the original ORCA025 grid (Maisonnavé et al., 2021).

But before replacing PISCES by MEDUSA, two preliminary tasks appeared necessary. Due to their complexity, these tasks represent most of the work that could be achieved during this support. The different steps, detailed by Maisonnavé and Berthet (2022) are summarized hereafter.

One task realized deals with the upgrade of the NEMO coarsened code from 3.6 to 4.2 version. Regarding the OASIS interface itself, it was overall quite simple to re-implement it in NEMO 4.2 as one of its design principle is to be as little intrusive as possible. However, definition of the coarsened model input files and weight-and-address files used for the regridding was less straightforward because of a new management of row- and column-duplicated lines for periodical conditions, particularly complex in the North Pole folding area.

Figure 2 shows, for example, the correspondance between the cells of the original ORCA025 grid and the coarsened ORCA075 grid with a zoom at the North pole folding.

The definition of a new coarsened ORCA075 grid involved the definition of new coarsened input files. To address this point, Mercator Océan developments based on the Fortran90 package AGRIF (Adaptive Grid Refinement In Fortran, (Debreu et al., 2012)) that allow to produce coarsened input files, such as the bathymetry, the 3D land sea mask or the fixed horizontal scale factors, were considered. Indeed, in addition to coupling by OASIS, using AGRIF is another strategy to implement coarsening in NEMO and it therefore seemed natural to mutualize this pre-processing step, required for both strategies. The `DOMAINCfg` AGRIF tool and related modifications were introduced and validated in the OASIS coarsening branch under git⁴. One has to take care, however, that this algorithm can still produce slightly unrealistic coarse bathymetry, for example opening isthmus or closing straights.

Finally, it was necessary to refurbish the existing tool that creates the weight-and-address regridding files. The two source and target land-sea masks are read from their corresponding meshmask files (produced in a

³<https://sasip-climate.github.io>

⁴<https://forge.nemo-ocean.eu/nemo/nemo/-/tree/85-bgc-coarsening-with-oasis>

Figure 2: Cells of an original ORCA025 grid (left) and its corresponding $\times 3$ coarsened ORCA075 grid (right) around the North pole folding. The last NjOglo row has been added on the ORCA075 grid to duplicate the NjOglo-2 row so to respect the North pole folding. For each grid, duplicated cells are represented with the same but lighter colour than the original ones. For example, for the ORCA075 grid, the light salmon cell at the top left duplicates the salmon cell at the bottom right.

first step by the DOMAINcfg tool), the coherence of the two grids is checked (pivot type, dimensions), and the coarsening algorithm applied to associate source grid points to every non masked target grid point.

The modifications were validated by comparing the results of two one-month long simulations run with the ORCA025-ORCA075 configuration in one hand and with the ORCA025 full resolution mono-executable on the other hand. No major differences were noticeable, which validates the interfaces and coarsening algorithms at first order.

The upgraded ocean-BGC coarsening interface in NEMO 4.2 is now able to provide coherent ocean variables to the BGC module and MEDUSA can now replace PISCES. But work still has to be devoted to ensure the exact conservation of oceanic quantities at the interface. From the numerical performance point of view, it would be interesting to try to reduce the accuracy (single precision) or the number of 3D scale factors exchanges, thus limit the coupling overhead (usually between 10% and 30% of the run time for that type of 3D coupling).

4.2 XIOS

The first call for XIOS Dedicated User Support was opened in 2019 but did not receive any application. The 2 PMs allocated for that support were transferred to Task 3.4 “Service 3: Weather and climate benchmarking” and served to measure the performance of the regridding library included in XIOS and to compare it with the performance of ESMF⁵ and SCRIP⁶ regridding libraries. Measurements of the time required to calculate the regridding weights for a specific pair of relatively high resolution grids were part of a larger benchmarking exercise on regridding libraries used in Earth System Models, which results are reported by Valcke et al. (2021b). The main conclusion is that both ESMF and XIOS have much better ($O(100)$) performance than the SCRIP. It also shows XIOS seems more performant than ESMF at low numbers of cores but this was probably linked to the fact that the XIOS measure did not include the time to write the weights to disk.

⁵Earth System Modelling Framework (ESMF), <https://earthsystemmodeling.org>

⁶Spherical Coordinate Remapping and Interpolation Package (SCRIP), <https://github.com/SCRIP-Project/SCRIP>

The second call offered 1 PM to the UK Met Office and 1 PM to Mercator Océan, and those supports are described hereafter.

4.2.1 Improved support of unstructured grids for UK Met Office LFRIC model

The full report on this service is available in Appendix 1.

The original aim was to allow the support of parametric vertical coordinates from the UGRID convention⁷ in XIOS. This was motivated by the use of XIOS in the next generation atmospheric model LFRIC using an unstructured “cubic sphere” mesh. However, it quickly appeared that the basic implementation in XIOS of the UGRID convention itself was covering only partially the Met Office needs and that the connectivity written in the output files for some elements was incorrect or inconsistent with the indexing of the model. It was therefore decided by mutual agreement to redirect the support toward a correct implementation in XIOS of the UGRID convention for LFRIC outputs.

Different developments and corrections regarding the representation of unstructured grid faces, edges and nodes connectivity in XIOS were then realized. A mini test case using the geometry of the cubic sphere grid emulating LFRIC model was developed and integrated in XIOS sources. At that point, as some problems still remained, the whole LFRIC model was ported on IDRIS supercomputer where the developers had access. Analysis of the code revealed an inconsistency in the mesh geometry provided to XIOS; corrections were proposed to the LFRIC developers and in XIOS that finally solved the problem (see Appendix 1 for details and LFRIC developers’ happy reactions). Those improvements and bug fixes for support of unstructured grids are now available in the last version of the IO server, XIOS3⁸.

In conclusion, that dedicated support, which was carried out in a very collaborative manner between NIWA (in New Zealand, Met Office collaborators), the Met Office and XIOS developers, lead to very satisfactory results for all parties within a reasonable timeframe of about 4 months.

4.2.2 Improvement of XIOS input for reading atmospheric forcing for Mercator Océan

The full report on this service is available in Appendix 2.

The request for dedicated support from Mercator Océan was motivated by the increase in resolution (x2 in horizontal) and output frequencies (from 6h to 1h) of the reanalysis files provided by the ECMWF in the transition from ERA-INTERIM to ERA5. Reading these new forcings had a major impact on the performance of NEMO with a slowdown of almost 40% of the code. In this support, it was proposed to replace the direct reads based on NetCDF by the asynchronous reads of XIOS and to evaluate the performance. At the same time, it was proposed to integrate the new XIOS3 version into NEMO in order to compare its performance and memory footprint compared with the XIOS2 version. After the integration of the reading functionalities by XIOS, the preliminary results show an acceleration of the reads by almost a factor of 3, for a total gain of the code of almost 26%. The switch from XIOS2 to XIOS3 showed significant gains of nearly 15% in speed-up for an equivalent configuration. In addition, the study showed a reduction of up to a factor of 3 in the memory footprint on XIOS servers.

4.3 Cylc

The Met Office originally offered 2 lots of 3 PMs for dedicated user support for Cylc and Rose. The first lot was awarded to ICM (Poland) in June 2021 for assistance in design and optimisation of the general workflow of ICM coupled model. The second lot was awarded to NCAS-CMS, University of Reading, UK in May 2022 to help with the installation of Cylc and Rose on ARCHER2 and migration to Cylc-8.

⁷<http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/cf-conventions.html#parametric-v-coord>

⁸<http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/browser/XIOS3/branches/xios-3.0-beta>

4.3.1 Support for design and optimisation of the general workflow of ICM coupled model with Cylc

The support requested was assistance in the design and optimisation of a complex modelling workflow focussing particularly on: 1) an efficient use of computing resources with maximum possible parallelization of different tasks, and 2) automated methods for error handling and managing delays.

After the initial meetings, it became clear that, rather than a short period of concentrated effort, the best way to support the work was to provide consultancy over a longer period (answering questions and investigating problems as and when they occurred). This is why only 1 PM of effort has been provided so far. Although support will go on until the end of ESiWACE2, it is clear that the initial planned effort of 3 PMs will not be spent. But as this support consist of a longer period consultancy, we see it finalised by the end of the project.

Progresses to date include:

- A series of virtual meetings have been held initially and a chat room on Element (<https://element.io>) was setup to allow discussion.
- The Met Office have been given accounts on the ICM systems.
- Access to the ICM gitlab has been given to allow collaboration on workflow configurations and documentation.
- ICM has worked on a workflow design with input from the Met Office.

The design has evolved through a series of detailed technical discussions both in meetings and via the chat room. Some of the error scenarios were quite challenging, for example:

- There are multiple HPC platforms available for running the models - if the primary system goes down the workflow should automatically re-run the appropriate tasks on the backup system.
- Sometimes one of the HPC nodes can have issues resulting in slow running of the model. In this case, the job needs to be killed and resubmitted with the defective node excluded.

The solution being prototyped involves having tasks which monitor the state of the system and can issue the appropriate commands to Cylc to remove tasks, reset task states, trigger tasks and alter job directives as needed.

- Prototyping has been done with Cylc-7 but the aim is to switch over to Cylc-8 (which may make some of the interventions easier to manage).
- After the release of Cylc-8 the Met Office gave a presentation on the key features and changes, so to facilitate ICM migration from Cylc-7 to Cylc-8.
- An initial installation of Cylc-8 was setup for testing / evaluation.

The next steps are:

- Continue to evolve the workflow design.
- Ensure an up to date installation of Cylc-8 is in place.
- Investigate any barriers to migrating the workflow to Cylc-8.

4.3.2 Support to NCAS (UK) for installation of Cylc and Rose on ARCHER2 and migration to Cylc-8

The second lot was awarded to NCAS-CMS, University of Reading, UK in May 2022.

The support requested was on the installation and configuration of Cylc-8 on the new PUMA server and training NCAS-CMS in Cylc-8 configuration and use. But during the initial meeting we identified that, although migration to Cylc-8 is the longer term aim, the immediate priority was to support use of the existing tools on the new PUMA server. Therefore, we agreed to extend the scope of the support to include assisting with the installation of the legacy tools Cylc-7 and Rose 2019.

Progresses to date include:

- Several meetings have been held remotely, including attending a meeting between NCAS and EPCC (the team responsible for providing the PUMA server).
- The proposed setup of the new PUMA server was reviewed to identify missing dependencies.
- The Met Office have been given accounts on the legacy PUMA server and the new PUMA server hosted on ARCHER2. Some initial setup and investigation work was performed.

Setting up the new PUMA server on ARCHER2 by the ARCHER2 support team took much longer than expected. Therefore most of the Cylc installation work had to be put on hold until beginning of January 2023. The work is ongoing and is expected to continue until the end of the ESiWACE 2 funding period although, but once again, only 1 PM of effort will most probably be spent until the end of the project.

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6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

One important difficulty faced during the project was the impossibility to offer on-site support because of the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore all supports were offered remotely. Even if this was not ideal, they turned out to be effective.

Another difficulty was to motivate applications from different groups, in particular outside ESIWACE2 and Western Europe, even if we made our best to advertise the service through different channels (mail to different lists, website, Twitter, personal communications, etc.).

The calls for support on OASIS3-MCT were treated jointly with the IS-ENES3 project offering similar service. In 2020, 5 research groups, all from Western Europe, responded to the call; given the 3 x 1-month support offered by IS-ENES3, only one group from Germany could not be served. In 2022, there was again 5 applicants for 4 available services and only a group from South America was not retained.

As written above, the first XIOS call in 2019 did not even get any application and the equivalent effort was transferred to Task 3.4 (see section 4.2 above). The second call was more successful with 4 applications; two were rejected (one from Italy, one from France) and the original 2 PM support was split into 2 supports of 1 PM to serve the Met Office and Mercator Océan.

The Cylc calls motivated each time in 2021 and 2022 only one applicant. However, even if the number of applicants was small, the quality of the successful applications were high, as evaluated by the selection committee, and this comfort us in the perspective that the delivered service would be useful.

Finally, as detailed in section 4.3, the originally 2 X 3 PMs for service on Cylc originally planned could not be delivered in the timeframe of the project. This is mainly linked for ICM to the fact that, rather than a short period of concentrated effort, the best way to support the work was to provide consultancy over a longer period. For NCAS, the main reason is the delay in setting up the new PUMA server on ARCHER2.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The services offered by ESIWACE2 to weather and climate modelling groups on coupling, IO, and workflow tools leveraged the use of these technologies in their respective Earth System Models. The services therefore help those groups to optimally use existing supercomputers and pre-exascale systems onto which these models are executed and thereby enhance the HPC capacity of the weather and climate community. These services also help the community to manage data produced by those simulation, the XIOS IO server and the Cylc workflow engine being an important part of the overall data production toolchain.

8 Sustainability

The services described in this deliverable constitute a transfer of specific knowledge from ESiWACE2 experts to the community. In turn, they help the tool developer to improve their software according to the community needs. As the services imply a tight interaction between the tool developers and the Earth System Model developers, there is no doubt that the improvements realised during the service will be maintained and further developed.

The services offered on OASIS3-MCT allowed to set the basis of two new types of coupling, one between an ocean model and two hemispheric sea-ice models, and a 3D one between an ocean model and a biogeochemistry module. Both couplings target coupled models that are involved in research projects, e.g. SASIP (Schmidt Futures) and OptimESM (Horizon Europe) respectively, and will certainly be heavily used to produce different simulations. The services on XIOS have the specificity to help the user groups while further developing the tool, i.e. full support of unstructured grids for the Met Office and improvement of the input functionality for Mercator Océan; these developments are already included in the official XIOS sources, which ensure an easy use for other groups and long-term sustainability. Finally, the services on Cylc targeted two groups that have chosen Cylc for managing the workflow of their official Earth System Model (at ICM and NCAS) and that will therefore build on the improvements realised during the service.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

The service calls and results were announced on the ESiWACE web site⁹. Specific reports were produced detailing the results of the services on OASIS3-MCT, see (Maisonnave and Berthet, 2022) and (Maisonnave and Bourdallé-Badie, 2022). The BGC related service will be presented during the DRAKKAR international ocean modelling workshop (Berthet et al.). For XIOS and Cylc, details of the services are presented in the current document.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A

⁹see <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support>

Appendices

1 Report: Improved support of unstructured grids for UK Met office LFRIC model

XIOS dedicated support report -LFRIC model-

Introduction

The Met Office is actively developing its next generation atmospheric model LFRIC to replace the current Met Office Unified Model (UM) with the objective of building a versatile and scalable weather and climate modelling infrastructure targeted at future machine architectures. LFRIC is built on top of the new "Gung-Ho" dynamical core revisiting the resolution of the primitive equations on the sphere with recent, more efficient and accurate numerical schemes, while freeing itself from the singularity at the pole of the former "EndGame" dynamical core based on a regular longitude-latitude grid. LFRIC adopted an unstructured mesh based on the refinement of the cubic sphere. For the model outputs, it was decided to explore the potential of XIOS for the performance aspects thanks to its asynchronous parallel read/write capabilities but also for its ability to manage unstructured meshes and to write them in NETCDF format, either according to the CF convention (<https://cfconventions.org>), or the UGRID convention (<https://ugrid-conventions.github.io/ugrid-conventions>). The UGRID convention is richer than the CF convention (on which it is built) because it informs the connectivity between the different elements of the mesh: faces, edges and nodes. It is this last convention that has been retained for the LFRIC outputs. The use of the UGRID convention through XIOS does not require direct information on connectivity, as XIOS is able to find it by itself, simply from the coordinates of the individual elements making up the mesh. This considerably simplifies the type of information to be provided, particularly in the context of a parallel model in distributed memory (MPI), since connectivity requires remote neighbourhood information which is not necessarily held by the local process.

A UGRID domain can be defined in the following way through the XIOS XML skeleton:

```
<domain_definition>
  <domain id="node" name="Mesh2d" nvertex="1" type="unstructured" />
  <domain id="edge" name="Mesh2d" nvertex="2" type="unstructured" />
  <domain id="face" name="Mesh2d" nvertex="4" type="unstructured" />
</domain_definition>
```

The coordinates of the edges and centre of the elements are provided dynamically from the model through the Fortran interface:

```
call xios_set_domain_attr( "face", lonvalue_id=lon_data, latvalue_id=lat_data,
  bounds_lonvalue_id=bounds_lon, bounds_latvalue_id=bounds_lat)
```

The name of the mesh determined by the attribute "**name**" (**Mesh2d**) defines that each of the elements node, edge and face belongs to the same common mesh. The value indicating the number of vertices constituting the element determines its nature: **nvertex="1"** → node, **nvertex="2"** → edge, **nvertex > "3"** → face. With this information, XIOS is able to automatically deduce the connectivity: face↔face, face↔edge, face↔node, edge↔face, edge↔edge, edge↔node, node↔node in order to write it in the output files as associated metadata. As an example, the header of a NETCDF file in UGRID format for the LFRIC project is provided in the appendix.

The initial request for XIOS support from the Met-Office concerned the management of auxiliary coordinates for vertical axes:

"We wish to make use of the other coordinate systems described in the CF standard, namely parametric vertical coordinates (<http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/cf-conventions.html#parametric-v-coord>) which require multiple sets of coordinates on the same axis for a given field. In addition to spatial coordinates, similar functionality would also be useful for temporal coordinates."

However, very soon after starting the support request, we realised that the implementation of the XIOS UGRID convention only partially covered the needs of the Met-Office and that the connectivity written in the output files for some elements was incorrect or inconsistent with the indexing of the model. We therefore decided, by mutual agreement, to redirect the support request toward a correct implementation of the UGRID convention for LFRIC output, which we considered to be a higher priority and more critical than the initial request.

Summary of the support process

Involvement of the XIOS team: 1 person-month

Support period: ~4 months: 24/06/2021 -> 28/10/2021

People involved :

- Met Office: E. Hone (PI), J.C. Rioual, S. Mullerworth, C. Johnson
- NIWA (New Zeland) : A. Pletzer, W. Hayek
- XIOS team (IPSL): Y. Meurdesoif, J. Drouillat

Meeting (virtual): 1 (kickoff)

Mail exchange: 140 (96 received, 34 sent)

Nature of support: debugging, code analysis (LFRIC and XIOS), development.

Deliverable: version of XIOS allowing the complete implementation of the LFRIC model outputs following the UGRID convention (3 commits, 123 code lines added/modified)

Technical details

- Clarification in the XIOS xml control files of the representation of faces, edges and nodes in order to obtain correct UGRID outputs.
- Added missing mesh connectivity (commit r2181): it was found that the metadata for defining face-face, face-edge and edge-face connectivity was missing.
- Then, we found that the indexing of the output data fields was not consistent with the definition of the connectivity.
- To better understand and solve the problem, development of a XIOS mini test case using the geometry of the cubic sphere, emulating the LFRIC model.
- After analysis, it appeared that local indexing (when using the domain attribute `i_index`) was not considered in the construction of connectivity. Furthermore, when the mesh defined faces, edges and nodes jointly, the consistency of the connectivity between each of its elements was not ensured.
- Correction of the problems analysed previously and integration of the cubic sphere test case in the r2200 commit (08/19/2021).
- Despite the fact that the cubic sphere test case gives now consistent results, the results on the LFRIC model still remain incorrect on some connectivity, despite a clear overall improvement.
- Recovery and installation of the LFRIC software stack on the French supercomputers (IDRIS) by the XIOS team. Run of a LFRIC test case highlighting the problem (IO_Dev miniapp).

Figure 1: Evidence of a problem in the geometry of the mesh provided to XIOS

- Analysis of the code reveals an inconsistency in the mesh geometry provided to XIOS. A correction is proposed to the LFRIC developers.

1. There is an implicit assumption that a cell's first edge (edge 1) is bounded the cells first and second nodes, this is not correct. Cell-wise, the indexing of the edges and vertices look like this:

```

4----4----3
:      :
1  1  3
:      :
1----2----2

```

so the first edge is bounded by the first and last nodes. Therefore lines 652-659 in `lfric_xios_io_mod` should be changed to:

```

! Retrieve the lat / lon coords of the points bounding the edge
if (df_x == 1) then
  edge1 = ndf_x/2
  edge2 = 1
else
  edge1 = df_x - 1
  edge2 = df_x
endif

```

Figure 2: Proposed correction on the LFRIC side

- After the correction on the LFRIC model side, there are still inconsistencies in connectivity between faces/edges and the output fields still appear blurred.

Figure 3: Graphical highlighting of inconsistencies in connectivity. Some fields appear scrambled.

- Finally, the last XIOS problems were identified and corrected in commit r2250 (10/25/2021).

Figure 4: The same field as before after the last XIOS correction

- After this modification all fields and connectivities are fully consistent within the same XIOS file following the UGRID convention.
- The changes initially made to the XIOS2/trunk branch were finally carried over to the XIOS3 version in the new release (commit r2417, 10/06/2022).

Brilliant, that does indeed fix the problem (see screenshot of the W2H field, with edges averaged over faces, as always) - thanks so much for all the hard work that you put into resolving this issue, Ed and Yann, that should be worth a celebration!! (W. Hayek)

Conclusion

This request for support was carried out in a very collaborative manner between NIWA, Met Office and IPSL to achieve a satisfactory result in the interest of all parties within a reasonable timeframe (~4 months). The LFRIC model team now has the possibility to produce its outputs in an unstructured format following the UGRID convention, using the full potential of XIOS. The XIOS team has consolidated its expertise around the UGRID convention and has made substantial corrections and improvements to the code that will increase its robustness and will be useful to other communities.

As we have deviated from the initial request concerning parametric vertical coordinates in the CF convention, we will propose to implement these missing functionalities during 2023 in the new XIOS3 version, as this request goes far beyond the LFRIC model.

This work will benefit the wider IS-ENES3 community, particularly modelling centres developing new applications on unstructured meshes.

Appendix: Typical header of an output file from the LFRIC model implementing the netcdf-UGRID convention

```
netcdf io_dev_diag {
dimensions:
    axis_nbounds = 2 ;
    Two = 2 ;
    nMesh2d_node = 56 ;
    nMesh2d_edge = 108 ;
    nMesh2d_face = 54 ;
    nMesh2d_vertex = 4 ;
    full_levels = 4 ;
    half_levels = 3 ;
    multi_data_axis = 5 ;
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
variables:
    int Mesh2d ;
        Mesh2d:cf_role = "mesh_topology" ;
        Mesh2d:long_name = "Topology data of 2D unstructured mesh" ;
        Mesh2d:topology_dimension = 2 ;
        Mesh2d:node_coordinates = "Mesh2d_node_x Mesh2d_node_y" ;
        Mesh2d:edge_coordinates = "Mesh2d_edge_x Mesh2d_edge_y" ;
        Mesh2d:edge_node_connectivity = "Mesh2d_edge_nodes" ;
        Mesh2d:face_edge_connectivity = "Mesh2d_face_edges" ;
        Mesh2d:edge_face_connectivity = "Mesh2d_edge_face_links" ;
        Mesh2d:face_face_connectivity = "Mesh2d_face_links" ;
        Mesh2d:face_coordinates = "Mesh2d_face_x Mesh2d_face_y" ;
        Mesh2d:face_node_connectivity = "Mesh2d_face_nodes" ;
    float Mesh2d_node_x(nMesh2d_node) ;
        Mesh2d_node_x:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        Mesh2d_node_x:long_name = "Longitude of mesh nodes." ;
        Mesh2d_node_x:units = "degrees_east" ;
    float Mesh2d_node_y(nMesh2d_node) ;
        Mesh2d_node_y:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        Mesh2d_node_y:long_name = "Latitude of mesh nodes." ;
        Mesh2d_node_y:units = "degrees_north" ;
    float Mesh2d_edge_x(nMesh2d_edge) ;
        Mesh2d_edge_x:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        Mesh2d_edge_x:long_name = "Characteristic longitude of mesh edges." ;
        Mesh2d_edge_x:units = "degrees_east" ;
    float Mesh2d_edge_y(nMesh2d_edge) ;
        Mesh2d_edge_y:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        Mesh2d_edge_y:long_name = "Characteristic latitude of mesh edges." ;
        Mesh2d_edge_y:units = "degrees_north" ;
    int Mesh2d_edge_nodes(nMesh2d_edge, Two) ;
        Mesh2d_edge_nodes:cf_role = "edge_node_connectivity" ;
        Mesh2d_edge_nodes:long_name = "Maps every edge/link to two nodes that it connects." ;
        Mesh2d_edge_nodes:start_index = 0 ;
    float Mesh2d_face_x(nMesh2d_face) ;
        Mesh2d_face_x:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        Mesh2d_face_x:long_name = "Characteristic longitude of mesh faces." ;
        Mesh2d_face_x:units = "degrees_east" ;
    float Mesh2d_face_y(nMesh2d_face) ;
        Mesh2d_face_y:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        Mesh2d_face_y:long_name = "Characteristic latitude of mesh faces." ;
        Mesh2d_face_y:units = "degrees_north" ;
    int Mesh2d_face_nodes(nMesh2d_face, nMesh2d_vertex) ;
        Mesh2d_face_nodes:cf_role = "face_node_connectivity" ;
        Mesh2d_face_nodes:long_name = "Maps every face to its corner nodes." ;
        Mesh2d_face_nodes:start_index = 0 ;
    int Mesh2d_face_edges(nMesh2d_face, nMesh2d_vertex) ;
        Mesh2d_face_edges:cf_role = "face_edge_connectivity" ;
        Mesh2d_face_edges:long_name = "Maps every face to its edges." ;
        Mesh2d_face_edges:start_index = 0 ;
        Mesh2d_face_edges:_FillValue = 999999 ;
```

```

int Mesh2d_edge_face_links(nMesh2d_edge, Two) ;
    Mesh2d_edge_face_links:cf_role = "edge face connectivity" ;
    Mesh2d_edge_face_links:long_name = "neighbor faces for edges" ;
    Mesh2d_edge_face_links:start_index = 0 ;
    Mesh2d_edge_face_links:FillValue = -999 ;
    Mesh2d_edge_face_links:comment = "missing neighbor faces are indicated using FillValue" ;
int Mesh2d_face_links(nMesh2d_face, nMesh2d_vertex) ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:cf_role = "face face connectivity" ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:long_name = "Indicates which other faces neighbor each face" ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:start_index = 0 ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:FillValue = 999999 ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:flag_values = -1 ;
    Mesh2d_face_links:flag_meanings = "out_of_mesh" ;
float full_levels(full_levels) ;
    full_levels:name = "full_levels" ;
float half_levels(half_levels) ;
    half_levels:name = "half_levels" ;
double time(time) ;
    time:axis = "T" ;
    time:standard_name = "time" ;
    time:long_name = "Time axis" ;
    time:calendar = "360_day" ;
    time:units = "seconds since 0000-01-01 00:00:00" ;
    time:time_origin = "0000-01-01 00:00:00" ;
    time:bounds = "time_bounds" ;
double time_bounds(time, axis_nbounds) ;
double W2V_field(time, full_levels, nMesh2d_face) ;
    W2V_field:long_name = "Field on W2-vertical function space" ;
    W2V_field:units = "1" ;
    W2V_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    W2V_field:location = "face" ;
    W2V_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    W2V_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    W2V_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    W2V_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    W2V_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_face_y Mesh2d_face_x" ;
double W2H_field(time, half_levels, nMesh2d_edge) ;
    W2H_field:long_name = "Field on W2-horizontal function space" ;
    W2H_field:units = "1" ;
    W2H_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    W2H_field:location = "edge" ;
    W2H_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    W2H_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    W2H_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    W2H_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    W2H_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_edge_y Mesh2d_edge_x" ;
double W3_field(time, half_levels, nMesh2d_face) ;
    W3_field:long_name = "Field on W3 function space" ;
    W3_field:units = "1" ;
    W3_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    W3_field:location = "face" ;
    W3_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    W3_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    W3_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    W3_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    W3_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_face_y Mesh2d_face_x" ;
double W3_2D_field(time, nMesh2d_face) ;
    W3_2D_field:long_name = "Two dimensional field on W3 function space" ;
    W3_2D_field:units = "1" ;
    W3_2D_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    W3_2D_field:location = "face" ;
    W3_2D_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    W3_2D_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    W3_2D_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    W3_2D_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    W3_2D_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_face_y Mesh2d_face_x" ;
double W0_field(time, full_levels, nMesh2d_node) ;
    W0_field:long_name = "Field on W0 function space" ;
    W0_field:units = "1" ;
    W0_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    W0_field:location = "node" ;
    W0_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    W0_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    W0_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    W0_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    W0_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_node_y Mesh2d_node_x" ;
double multi_data_field(time, multi_data_axis, nMesh2d_face) ;
    multi_data_field:long_name = "Multi-data (ndata=5) field on W3, 2D function space" ;
    multi_data_field:units = "1" ;
    multi_data_field:mesh = "Mesh2d" ;
    multi_data_field:location = "face" ;
    multi_data_field:online_operation = "instant" ;
    multi_data_field:interval_operation = "86400 s" ;
    multi_data_field:interval_write = "86400 s" ;
    multi_data_field:cell_methods = "time: point" ;
    multi_data_field:coordinates = "Mesh2d_face_y Mesh2d_face_x" ;

// global attributes:
    :name = "io_dev_diag" ;
    :description = "Created by xios" ;
    :title = "Created by xios" ;
    :Conventions = "UGRID" ;
    :timeStamp = "2021-Oct-28 08:19:34 GMT" ;
    :uuid = "8671f09f-a560-4f80-9a68-55b08d7e7a36" ;
}

```


2 Report: Improvement of XIOS input for reading atmospheric forcing for Mercator Océan

Improvement of XIOS input for reading atmospheric forcing for Mercator Océan

Summary of support process

This activity consisted in integrating in NEMO a system for reading atmospheric forcing with XIOS, the existing system does not scale. The implementation of this system relied on a small case (ORCA2), which allowed to identify the data to be specified in the XML file and to develop the associated Fortran code. The developments have been tested on a larger scale with an ORCA025 configuration. We took advantage of this collaboration to test XIOS3 on a real simulation code.

The NEMO request

“Help to choose the best strategy to implement atmospheric forcing reading in Nemo model, depending on XIOS possibilities & limitations in order to solve scalability issues created by the actual interface (io-ipsl).”

“In this example, a surface timestep duration lasts twice as long as a computation timestep for ~1000 processors, and this factor increases up to 6 for 6000 processors.”

Involvement of the XIOS team: 1 person-month

People involved: G. Samson (NEMO/Mercator, PI), S. Masson (NEMO/LOCEAN), J. Dérouillat (XIOS/IPSL), Y. Meurdesoif (XIOS/IPSL)

Support period: ~ 5 months: 20/07/2022 -> 16/12/2022

Meeting: 1 face to face, 3 virtual

Mail exchange: 141 (68 received, 73 sent)

Nature of support: development, performance testing

From XIOS 2 to XIOS3

The decision was taken to work on the fields forcing of NEMO using XIOS3 because it is known that the coupling of NEMO and XIOS is greedy regarding memory. One of the XIOS3 improvement concern the memory management, it could provide more flexibility regarding at the XIOS usage.

The porting of NEMO to XIOS3 consists in disabling, temporarily, the tiling introduced in NEMO for OpenMP. A preprocessing key “**key_xios3**” has been introduced to protect calls to XIOS2 routine related to tiling.

The tiling has not been backported yet in XIOS3. An implementation based on the new XIOS infrastructure (using connectors, views to go from model’s tiled data to XIOS oriented “packed” data) is planned, it is seen has a good way to support OpenMP in the future.

Some attributes were directly defined on **field_definition** (**file_definition**), it was advised to move these attributes to dedicated **field_group** “**all_fields**” (respectively **file_group**). All fields defined within a **field_definition** will inherit from **element_definition**, whatever the context. The following line has been replaced :

```
<field_definition level="1" prec="4" operation="average" enabled=".TRUE." default_value="1.e20" > <!-- time step automaticaly defined -->
```

By :

```
<field_definition> <!-- time step automaticaly defined -->
<field_group id="all_fields" level="1" prec="4" operation="average" enabled=".TRUE." default_value="1.e20" >
```

Reading atmospheric forcing

A. NEMO

The `fld_update` routine calls by `fld_read`, which manages forcing input fields (reads, temporal and spatial interpolations), hosts the connection of XIOS reads (for now using a preprocessing key `key_xios3`).

Calls to `xios_rcv_field` will be operated through `fld_xios_get` which is mainly an interface to `iom_xios_get(_123d)`, a generic routine whose aim is to receive fields from XIOS. Its implementation is based on an implementation of a restart system using XIOS.

At the end, `iom_nf90_xios_get (iom_nf90_xios_g123d_dp)` is the generic wrapper to `xios_rcv_field`, regarding dimension.

B. XML

Forcing fields needed by NEMO are specified in a dedicated XML file included in the “nemo” context. It contains the information on the 9 fields required by NEMO, below: the management of `u10` (the wind component).

```
<field_definition>
  <field_group domain_ref="to_grid_T" read_access="true" default_value="0" >
    <field id="u10_int0" field_ref="u10_0" />
    <field id="u10_int1" field_ref="u10_1" />
    <field id="u10_int" field_ref="u10" />
  </field_group>
</field_definition>

<file_definition>
  <file_group type="one_file" mode="read" >
    <file name="ERA5_BULKU10M_1H_extrap_y2012m09" output_freq="100y" record_offset="719" >
      <field id="u10_0" name="u10" freq_offset="1ts" operation="once" domain_ref="era5" />
    </file>
    <file name="ERA5_BULKU10M_1H_extrap_y2012m10" output_freq="100y" record_offset="0" >
      <field id="u10_1" name="u10" freq_offset="1ts" operation="once" domain_ref="era5" />
    </file>
    <file name="ERA5_BULKU10M_1H_extrap_y2012m10" output_freq="1h" record_offset="1" >
      <field id="u10" name="u10" freq_offset="1ts" operation="instant" domain_ref="era5" />
    </file>
  </file_group>
</file_definition>

<domain_definition>
  <domain id="era5" type="rectilinear" >
    <generate_rectilinear_domain/>
  </domain>
  <domain id="to_grid_T" domain_ref="grid_T" >
    <interpolate_domain order="1" renormalize="true" />
  </domain>
</domain_definition>
```

The fields received by NEMO, are suffixed using “_int”, they are defined on the NEMO grid called “`grid_T`” while data extracted from the file are defined on the “`era5`” grid. The fields interpolations are then operated in parallel by XIOS clients.

For now, the interpolations concern the spatial dimension, not the temporal one. The temporal interpolations are managed by NEMO itself using for a single data (here `u10`), 3 XIOS fields specified with different time record (“`record_offset`”). The fields suffixed using “_`(int)0`” and “_`(int)1`” will be

used to initialize the simulation (**operation="once"**), while the main field will be read regularly and interpolated with the previous field read.

The management of the temporal interpolations is a feature which is in the XIOS roadmap.

C. Performances

The new protocol has been benchmarked on a iORCA025 configuration (1440x1049x75 grid points) which runs on 1242 NEMO process using 34 XIOS process on TGCC (Irene Skylake) during a month of simulated time. To evaluate its integration, the average time per reading timestep is compared to the average time per non-reading timestep in Figure 1, as in the figure of the proposal provided to start this project.

This study has been performed without time interpolations, this have no consequences regarding the amount of data read or on the frequency of reading, but it may decrease the computation part of a timestep.

protocol	time (s) per timesteps Considered : ALL		time (s) per timesteps Considered : READ		time (s) per timesteps Considered : NOT READ	
	"LEGACY"	XIOS	"LEGACY"	XIOS	"LEGACY"	XIOS
min	0.21	0.21	0.58	0.28	0.21	0.21
max	1.78	16.24	1.78	16.24	1.31	1.41
avg	0.41	0.30	0.78	0.40	0.23	0.26
time saved		26.37%		48.65%		-11.03%

Figure 1: Comparison of the reading cost : XIOS is compared to the protocol used up to now. Timestep times are differentiated according to whether they are reading or not

With XIOS, reading times can't be compared directly between the 2 protocols, a part of the "READ" time can be accumulated during "NOT READ" timesteps, see in Figure 1 the 11% gap between "LEGACY" and XIOS on "NOT READ" timesteps in the last double column of the figure. This is due to the asynchronism of XIOS.

To measure more fairly the XIOS read time (in Figure 2), we first consider that the pure non-reading time is the "LEGACY" one : XIOS average times per timestep are corrected considering that during the simulation 1 in 3 timesteps is a "READ" timestep.

protocol	time (s) per timesteps Considered : ALL		time (s) per timesteps Considered : READ		time (s) per timesteps Considered : NOT READ	
	"LEGACY"	XIOS (corrected)	"LEGACY"	XIOS (corrected)	"LEGACY"	XIOS (corrected)
min	0.21	0.21	0.58	0.28	0.21	0.21
max	1.78	16.24	1.78	16.24	1.31	1.41
avg	0.41	0.30	0.78	0.45	0.23	0.23
time saved		26.37%		42.08%		0.00%

Figure 2: Comparison of the reading cost corrected to take in account the XIOS asynchronism

Another remark on XIOS times concerns the maximum time of "READ" timesteps, During the simulation (2160 timesteps), 2 timesteps in 720 cost 35 times the average "READ" time. The 10th and the 148th : these costs can be considered as initialisation costs. They are due to internal XIOS management of buffers : first (at 10th) regarding input, secondly regarding output (the 148th timestep

is the first reading timestep after the 2nd output timestep, output are dailies with 72 timesteps per day). Results are shown in Figure 3.

protocol	time (s) per timesteps Considered : READ		Pure read time (s)	
	"LEGACY"	XIOS (corrected)	"LEGACY"	XIOS (corrected)
avg	0.78	0.41	0.54	0.18
XIOS speedup		1.90		3.06

Figure 3: Comparison of the reading cost considering full XIOS initialisation, especially feedback from the server side

Tests on larger configurations, on which the time degradation was larger have to be run.

Testing XIOS3

We took the opportunity from this collaboration to evaluate the behaviour of XIOS3 on a true model. A NEMO benchmark has been provided that has been set to stress the XIOS framework using a 1440 x 1680 x 75 grid to output usual NEMO fields (with 13 3D fields and 22 2D fields) every 50 timesteps (at this resolution, the output frequency should be closer to 80 timesteps). Overall, about 385 GB are written out.

A such configuration has been run on 2688 NEMO process, targeting 3% of XIOS process to cover the data management cost. To be more efficient to write files, the "timeseries" mode (splitting of fields in dedicated files) has been enabled in the XML configuration file:

```
<file_group id="50ts" output_freq="50ts" output_level="10" enabled=".TRUE." timeseries="only">
<file id="file11" name_suffix="_grid_T" description="ocean T grid variables" >
<field ts_enabled="true" field_ref="e3t"/>
```

A such configuration has been run on 2688 NEMO process, targeting 3% of XIOS process (80) to cover the diagnostics management cost, whose 16 are dedicated to level 2 (limited by the number of 3D output files, XML below). 2000 timesteps have been run to smooth the costly initialisation step.

```
<variable id="using_server2" type="bool">true</variable/>
<variable id="ratio_server2" type="int">20</variable>
```

A. Comparison with XIOS2

In Figure 4, timers are extracted from the XIOS internal profiling for the firsts : NEMO process "CLIENT 0", XIOS level 1 server "SERVER 0 (N1)" and XIOS level 2 server "SERVER 0 (N2)". Excepting the initialisation step ("Context : close definition"), the elapsed times are good with regard to reference. Note that the initialisation step of the N1 level has consequences on the client side, indeed while servers are not available to treat the clients data, the clients will at the end wait for the servers.

	1 XIOS Enabled = false	80 XIOS Using 16 N2	80 XIOS Using 16 N2
	Ref XIOS3	XIOS2	XIOS3
<i>time mpirun</i>	5m50.511	7m52.466s	6m43.617
CLIENT 0			
Time from XIOS init to XIOS finalize	342.46	462.87	390.21
Total time spent for XIOS	33.66	57.95	79.65
XIOS init context	10.21	0.18	9.28
Time spent for waiting free buffer	0.00	27.79	34.29
Ratio	0.00 %	6.00 %	8.79 %
SERVER 0 (N1)			
Total time spent for XIOS	347.04	462.54	397.95
Context : close definition	-	0.00	50.40
Time spent in processing events	0.03	396.42	123.56
Blocking time	-	324.61	39.14
Ratio	0.01 %	85.70 %	31.05 %
"XIOS init and finalize (client)" – close definition	342.46	462.87	339.81
SERVER 0 (N2)			
Total time spent for XIOS		462.63	397.33
Time spent in processing events		325.81	310.05
Files : writing data		65.93	104.59
Ratio		70.43 %	78.04 %

Figure 4: Impact of XIOS on a NEMO simulation. The reference (left column) was run with a single XIOS3 server disabling IO to enable the XIOS profiling (hence no numbers for N2 servers). The total time spent for XIOS is much less with XIOS3 than XIOS2. The overhead of ~50 secs for XIOS3 compared to the reference is mainly linked to the initialization phase (line "Context : close definition"). Outside this phase, the restitution time with XIOS3 is comparable to the reference.

Another good point concerns the efficiency of the workflow with XIOS3, this is illustrated by the low **blocking time** on the N1 servers while more time is used to write on N2 servers ("**Files : writing data**"). The analysis on this last point is in progress.

To summarize, axis of work to improve the behaviour of XIOS3 concerns:

- the initialisation of N1 servers: the distribution of fields (`field->sendFieldToFileServer()`) and files (`distributeFiles(this->enabledWriteModeFiles)`) do not scale as expected between N1 and N2 servers while it is the case between clients and N1 servers
- the NetCDF integration: being significantly less efficient than XIOS2 is reproducible while this part which can be seen as a pure back-end should not be impacted by the refactoring
- the optimisation of connectors which cost the major part of the time spent in processing events outside of waiting, writing and initialisation (details profiling not provided here have been generated)

B. Parallel write

Another study, in Figure 5, concerns the parallel usage of NetCDF which could be privileged to avoid timeseries or to assume the load of more N1 servers required by more clients (for instance with 15 x 15 domain, the benchmark is set with 30 x 30 domain).

		80 XIOS Using 16 N2 <i>default is 16 pools</i>	80 XIOS Without N2	80 XIOS Using 16 N2 Split in 4 pools
		XIOS3 6m43.617	XIOS3 After 7 min 250 ts / serveur 0	XIOS3 23m4.295s
CLIENT 0	Time from XIOS init to XIOS finalize	390.21		1,247.89
	Total time spent for XIOS	397.95		1,377.55
SERVER 0 (N1)	Time spent in processing events	123.56		920.39
	Blocking time	39.14		739.31
	Total time spent for XIOS	397.33		1376.22
SERVER 0 (N2)	Time spent in processing events	310.05		1331.04
	Files : writing data	104.59		1117.66

Figure 5: Impact of parallel write. In the second column, the 80 servers write concurrently; after 7 minutes, the configuration without N2 servers had run only about 10% of the timesteps and was killed. In the third column the 16 N2 servers have been split in 4 pools, each pool is in charge of an output file (timeseries disabled), a single write is operated concurrently by 4 servers.

The time required to run the full 2000 timesteps of the simulation with sequential write on N2 servers is 6min43sec (first column). After 7 minutes, the configuration without N2 servers had run only about 10% of the timesteps and was killed; no numbers are therefore available (middle column). Using less concurrency for parallel write (4 process per parallel write, right column) shows a significant loss of performance during write. This observation has been reinforced executing the [IOR](#) benchmark on 1, 2 and 4 process (Figure 6) : indeed the bandwidth is not aggregated as expected, but worst, in the relevant case for XIOS (“**HDF5 Collective**”), the bandwidth is reduced while the LUSTRE striping is set to 4. This malfunction is most probably inherent to the platform and not XIOS itself and the computing centre will be contacted on this issue.

	Bandwidth(MiB/s)				
	POSIX	HDF5 Independant	HDF5 Collective	MPIIO Independant	MPIIO Collective
1	1228.07	1154.76	901.56	1154.19	1028.6
2	1155.29	1164.72	331.52	1228.64	895.18
4	1574.83	1380.6	379.34	1590.44	886.13

Figure 6: Writing bandwidth estimated through the IOR benchmark (using 1 GiB blockSize per process, and 2 MiB transferSize)

Note that running the same benchmark, information is collected about reading bandwidth. Contrary to the case of writing, the bandwidth is here aggregated (Figure 7).

	Bandwidth (MiB/s)				
	POSIX	HDF5 Independent	HDF5 Collective	MPIIO Independent	MPIIO Collective
1	6075.16	5879.09	3879.1	6061.57	6009.05
2	11305.95	11188.17	5852.87	11356.15	7643.8
4	17186.63	18580.09	11339.68	20330.16	13675.07

Figure 7: Reading bandwidth estimated through the IOR benchmark (using 1 GiB blockSize per process, and 2 MiB transferSize)

C. Memory footprint

A major improvement of XIOS3 regarding XIOS2 consists in a better memory footprint. In Figure 8 an evaluation of the memory peak used by each kind of MPI process is shown.

	XIOS2	XIOS3
Client + Model	150 Mo	120 Mo
Server N1	3.75 Go	2 Go
Server N2	30 Go	10 Go

Figure 8: Memory consumption of process involving XIOS

The new XIOS3 version leads to reduce memory footprint of a factor 2 to 3 on server side compared to XIOS2. It leads also to decreasing memory footprint on client side, but we currently cannot separate the part of the memory consumed by XIOS and by NEMO, so cannot concluded to a ratio concerning only XIOS3 Vs XIOS2. This evaluation is provided through a probing system driven by XIOS triggered when some events occur. A timeline representing the memory consumption along the simulation time can be produced (Figure 9) for each MPI process.

Figure 9: Evolution of the memory consumption of a XIOS N1 server for the NEMO benchmark. At the top for XIOS3, at the bottom for XIOS2. Each point represents a XIOS event. Blue represents the virtual memory, orange the RSS and green the RSS peak (to cover unmonitored events).